

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PLANT SELF-DEFENSE SYSTEMS AGAINST NEGATIVE FACTORS

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Abstract

From a biological perspective, stress is considered as any change in the external environmental conditions that weakens the normal development of a plant or changes it in a negative direction [2]. Biotic (pathogen, competition with other organisms, etc.) and abiotic (drought, salinity, radiation, high and low temperatures, etc.) stresses cause changes in the physiological activity of plants, weaken the biosynthesis process in the cell, disrupt normal life activities and ultimately can cause the death of plants. Drought stress, being one of the most widespread environmental factors affecting development and productivity, induces many physiological, biochemical and molecular responses in plants and plants form tolerant mechanisms to adapt to unfavorable environmental conditions. The study of these mechanisms is of great theoretical and experimental importance in the creation of plant varieties and forms resistant to unfavorable external environmental factors. All living organisms, including plants, are constantly exposed to the environmental factors they live in during their life activity. The responses of organisms to external environmental factors are of a general nature. These factors can be changes in natural conditions (drought, salinity, radiation, high and low temperatures, etc.), infectious factors (viruses, bacteria, etc.) or other anthropogenic factors. In order for plants to survive and continue their life activity, they must adapt to changed external environmental factors. In the process of evolution, various ways of adaptation of organisms to external environmental factors have arisen, but the mechanisms for perceiving and defending against these factors have not yet been fully elucidated.

Keywords: stress factor, plant, enzyme, biochemical processes

Introduction: As is known, most plants are doomed to a sedentary lifestyle. Therefore, they are often forced to be exposed to extreme environmental factors. Among such factors, one of the most important and widespread in nature is soil salinity, i.e. salt stress. Often, the salinity factor coincides with the drought factor and leads to an increase in the negative effect of salinity on plants. The occurrence of such acute stress leads to a slowdown in the growth and development of plants, a weakening of their vitality, a sharp decrease in their productivity, and in severe stress cases, to the destruction of plants [1,2,4]. One of the factors complicating the negative effect of the salinity factor on plants is that it enhances the effects of other stress factors, such as drought, intense light and high temperature. For this reason, salinity or salt stress is becoming a major problem limiting the productivity of agricultural plants, and its solution is one of the important and urgent issues in meeting the food needs of a growing population. According to estimates, the world population will increase by 34% in 2050 to 9.1 billion, which will be accompanied by a 70% increase in people's food needs (FAO, 2009). At the beginning of the development cycle (ontogenesis), the seeds of plants that reproduce by seeds, including wheat, barley, beans and peas, are primarily exposed to the negative impact of extreme environmental conditions. It is clear that the subsequent stages of plant development are directly related to their ability to maintain germination in these unfavorable conditions. [3,9]. In this regard, undoubtedly, one of the main problems of interest in our research, as a starting point, was and should have

been to clarify the effect of the intended Na-isocationic salts, i.e., NaCl, Na₂SO₄, NaHCO₃ and Na₂CO₃ salt solutions, on the germination properties of the seeds of wheat, barley, beans and peas chosen as the object of research.

Conclusion and research: Effect of Na-isocationic salt solutions on the germination properties of wheat seeds

As already mentioned, one of the main objectives of the research was to study the effect of different concentrations of Na-isocationic salts on the germination of wheat seeds, the dynamics of the development of seedlings and the changes in the activity dynamics of enzymes, Q6PDH and DMDH, which are of great importance in the formation of the reducing potential of cells.

Figure 1 presents the results of experiments on the effect of NaCl, Na₂SO₄, NaHCO₃ and Na₂CO₃ salt solutions in the range of 0-100 mM concentrations on the germination percentage of wheat seeds. As can be seen from the figure, the germination of wheat seeds soaked in distilled water was 95%. Increasing the concentration of NaCl salt in the medium to 25 mM had almost no effect on the germination percentage of seeds. Doubling the salt concentration (50 mM) already began to exert its inhibitory effect on the germination percentage of seeds, and this effect became relatively stronger at subsequent concentrations. Thus, the germination percentage in the 50 mM NaCl salt solution decreased by 14.7% compared to the control variant, and in the 100 mM concentration by 24.2%.

Figure 1. Effect of NaCl, Na₂SO₄, NaHCO₃ and Na₂CO₃ salt solutions on the germination percentage of wheat seeds

As can be seen from the results obtained in connection with the study of the germination percentage, the NaCl salt solution did not have a very sharp negative effect on the germination of wheat seeds at the level of 50 and 100 mM, that is, although certain difficulties arose in the germination of seeds in relatively weakly saline soils based on NaCl salt, these difficulties were not catastrophic. [4,8]. The negative effect of Na₂SO₄ salt solutions on the germination ability of seeds was somewhat more pronounced than that of NaCl salt solutions. Its inhibitory effect on the course of this process began already at a concentration of 25 mM and became even stronger at subsequent concentrations. For example, 4% of seeds soaked in a 25 mM Na₂SO₄ salt solution, 18.9% of those soaked in a 50 mM solution, and 28.4% of those soaked in a 100 mM solution lost their germination ability. As can be seen from the figures presented, Na₂SO₄ salt solutions at similar concentrations always had a slightly stronger negative effect on the germination of wheat seeds than NaCl salt solutions. Considering that the difference between the salts is related to their anion composition, it can be assumed that this effect is related to SO ions [3,6,7]. On the other hand, the amount of Na ions in Na₂SO₄ salt at the same molar concentration is twice as high as in NaCl salt solutions. This factor should not be overlooked. Among the tested salt solutions with Na-isocations, the solutions of NaHCO₃ and Na₂CO₃ salts had a sharply negative effect on the germination of wheat seeds. As can be seen from the figures presented in the figure, firstly, the degree of influence of both salt solutions on this process was almost close to each other, and secondly, at high concentrations of NaHCO₃ and Na₂CO₃ salts, unlike NaCl and Na₂SO₄ salt solutions, more than half of the seeds lost their germination properties. Thus, only 42% of the seeds in the 100 mM NaHCO₃ salt solution were able to retain their germination properties, and 40% in the 100 mM Na₂CO₃ salt solution.

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